

HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies

CONSULTATION REPORT

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Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the traditional custodians throughout Australia and their continuing connection to, and deep knowledge of, the land and waters. We pay our respects to Elders both past and present.

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Abbreviations

ACTA	Australian Clinical Trials Alliance
ADA	Australian Data Archive
AHRA	Australian Health Research Alliance
AIHW	Australian Institute of Health and Welfare
ANZCTR	Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
CHF	Consumers Health Forum
CQR	Clinical Quality Registries
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HDA	Health Data Australia
HeSANDA	Health Studies Australian National Data Asset
HREC	Human research ethics committee
IPD	Individual participant-level data
NHMRC	National Health and Medical Research Council
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
People RDC	People Research Data Commons
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SRE	Secure research environment

Executive summary

The Australian Research Data Commons ([ARDC](#)) is partnering with the health research community to build a national infrastructure to facilitate sharing of the data outputs of health studies. The Health Studies Australian National Data Asset ([HeSANDA](#)) program aims to support health data sharing and secondary use in a way that brings value to the research community; increase the impact of research; maximise the investment in health research; and provide health, economic and social benefits to Australia's population. The initiative has been supported by an external advisory committee consisting of: National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC), Research Australia, Cochrane Australia, Australian Health Research Alliance (AHRA), Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (ANZCTR), Australian Clinical Trials Alliance (ACTA), the Population Health Research Network (PHRN), and the Consumers Health Forum (CHF). HeSANDA development is incremental and builds consensus within the health research community and key stakeholders about the purpose, requirements, and practice guidelines for data sharing and secondary use.

In its initial phase (2020-2023), HeSANDA focused on investigator-initiated clinical trials data sharing and established partnerships with 72 organisations via nine 'Node' projects. The major output of this phase was the creation of [Health Data Australia](#) (HDA) - a national online platform to improve the findability of and access to data for research. Other key outcomes included: national metadata standards, community-agreed operating procedures to support data sharing, resources to obtain informed consent to share participant data, a clinical trials data sharing community of practice, and various outreach and training activities. In its next phase, ARDC seeks to extend the HeSANDA program to support other academic-led health studies such as health cohort studies and clinical quality registries (CQRs).

The extension of the HeSANDA program will form a key component of a larger portfolio of investment into national health research data infrastructure known as the [People Research Data Commons](#) (People RDC). The People RDC is establishing a series of coordinated infrastructure programs to address four key data challenges in: data strategy and data discovery, secure data access, data integration, and advanced analysis. As part of its strategic planning, ARDC held a series of consultation workshops with the health cohort study and Clinical Quality Registries (CQR) communities to assess the feasibility of extending the HeSANDA program to support them.

The health cohort study consultations¹ identified:

- In-principle research community support for HeSANDA's vision and the extension of the HeSANDA program to support cohort study research
- Data challenges and priorities for cohort research that align with the current scope of the HeSANDA program
- Data challenges and priorities for cohort research that align with the broader People RDC portfolio

Consequently, ARDC will look to undertake additional engagement with key stakeholder groups to refine the scope of an infrastructure program to support Australian health cohort studies.

¹ NB. Separate consultations were held with health cohort study and CQRs researchers. This document reports on the outcomes of the consultations with health cohort studies only. The outcomes of the CQR consultations will be reported separately.

Consultation report

Introduction

Background

The Health Studies Australian National Data Asset ([HeSANDA](#)) program was established to support the sharing of health data for research. To date, the program’s focus has been on supporting the curation of research outputs from investigator-initiated clinical trials in order to support their findability and access by secondary researchers (see Figure 1 below). During this first phase (2020-2023), HeSANDA established partnerships with 72 Australian research organisations via nine ‘Node’ projects.

Figure 1. The research journey for clinical trials. Blue highlights indicate the stages supported by the current HeSANDA program and infrastructure

The major output of this phase was the creation of [Health Data Australia](#) (HDA) - a national online platform to improve the findability of and access to clinical trials data for secondary research. A federated architecture was implemented, such that the Nodes and their partner organisations agreed to develop and/or modify their existing data management practices and systems to adhere to a common set of requirements that were developed by consensus. This allowed HeSANDA’s partners to determine how to implement the requirements in a way that best suited their existing operating environments.

To support the data sharing practices of clinical trials and enable them to join Health Data Australia, a number of other key outputs of the HeSANDA program included:

- national metadata standards;
- community-agreed operating procedures to support data sharing;
- resources to obtain informed consent to share participant data;
- a clinical trials data sharing community of practice;
- various outreach and training activities.

The establishment of Health Data Australia and HeSANDA’s other outputs was a response to priorities defined by the clinical trials research community², and resulted from an extensive consultative, co-development process with that community.

² ARDC. (2021). *HeSANDA Development Priorities: Research community consultation report*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559027>

Expansion of the HeSANDA program

Building on the success of the work with the clinical trials community, ARDC has undertaken consultations to assess the feasibility of expanding the HeSANDA program to support other academic-led health research studies. Based on guidance from the program advisory committee, workshops were held to investigate whether HeSANDA's scope, methods, and outputs aligned with the needs of the Australian health cohort study community. The workshops aimed to identify:

- Research purposes and use cases for the sharing of health cohort data
- Key requirements for the sharing of health cohort data
- A value proposition for national data sharing infrastructure for key stakeholders
- Barriers and enablers to successful infrastructure development and uptake
- Opportunities and priorities for infrastructure development activities

Public consultations were held across three workshops from July to September 2023 and were open to anyone from peak bodies and key stakeholders involved in cohort studies.

Consultation design

Participants

An open invitation to participate in the consultation workshops was extended to anyone affiliated with cohort studies or other research communities (e.g. research studies and longitudinal cohort studies) such as researchers, institutions, organisations, peak bodies and policy makers. Registration names, positions and organisations were reviewed in the weeks prior to the workshops to ensure a representative sample with the aim of reducing feedback bias. Participants were encouraged to attend all workshops.

The workshops were announced via:

- The ARDC website and newsletter
- Direct email to participants
- Distribution via HeSANDA Node affiliations

Workshop Attendance

Number of participants who attended as a percentage of registrations

Workshop	Date	Number of registrations	Number of registrants who attended	Percentage of registrants who attended
1	26.7.2023	71	37	52%
2	30.8.2023	79	37	46%
3	27.9.2023	78	25	32%

Attendee titles

CEO, COO, Directors, Project Managers, Data Managers, Research Professors/ Fellows/ Associates/ Managers, Policy Advisor, Software Engineer, Technical Manager, Lecturers, Librarian.

Organisation types

Number and type of organisation represented at each workshop

Workshop format and structure

The HeSANDA Expansion project consultation took a three step incremental approach via interactive online workshops with structured agenda topics and guided questions. The workshop included a moderated question & answer session and smaller breakout rooms to articulate responses from all participants.

- Workshop 1 - Introduce the HeSANDA program
 - Workshop one provided the audience with the background of the HeSANDA program which focussed on government funded investigator-initiated clinical trials and building infrastructure to support data discovery and accessibility. The focus of the breakout sessions was to determine the perspectives of the participants regarding benefits of sharing health research data for secondary purposes.
- Workshop 2 - Follow-up with key leads
 - Participants involved in the workshop were encouraged to continue their feedback via a breakout room, discuss the types of research outputs available and the barriers and enablers that impact data sharing.
- Workshop 3 - Focus on the HeSANDA infrastructure model built for clinical trials
 - During the final workshop participants were encouraged to identify existing standards for data sharing, gaps in standards and processes, and evaluate the current infrastructure model for its applicability and ease of integration.

Timing and frequency: Commencing July and finalised by October 2023 three workshops were conducted with one topic addressed each month.

Size: Max. 40-80 participants registered per workshop. Breakout group sessions contained 4 to 12 participants.

Duration: Approximately 90-minute sessions (per workshop)

Roles and responsibilities:

- ARDC Program Manager provided oversight, guidance, and acted as a breakout room facilitator.
- HeSANDA Program Coordinator arranged workshops, monitored event registration, identified gaps in audience, collated workshop feedback, liaised with all participants and breakout room facilitators, and created all documents required for the workshop.
- Workshop participants who registered to attend one or more workshops contributed to the consultation summary, priorities and principles in this report.
- Breakout room facilitators were responsible for guiding the structured questions, recording sessions, summarising the feedback, and reporting on the outcomes of each workshop.
- Editorial Team was responsible for reviewing the report and providing feedback on the outcomes.

Supporting documentation:

- Reference documents with the topic and key questions were circulated 1 week prior to the workshop event.
- Participants were provided an opportunity to submit feedback via email within 1 week following each workshop.

Workshop themes and questions

Workshop 1

- Theme: Benefits and motivators of data sharing
- Questions:
 - Would research/researchers benefit from being able to reuse YOUR health research data for secondary research purposes?
 - What benefits could you get from sharing data using a platform like Health Data Australia?
 - What motivates/would motivate you to share your data for secondary research purposes?

Workshop 2

- Theme: Types of research outputs available for sharing
- Question:
 - Identify the key types of research outputs and indicate which are essential for secondary users to have access to
- Theme: Issues or challenges
- Questions:
 - Identify barriers for data providers who wish to share these research outputs
 - Identify enablers for data providers who wish to share these research outputs

Workshop 3

- Theme: Existing data sharing practices standards, processes, policies and systems
- Question:
 - Identify which cohort studies have existing standards, processes, policies and systems
- Theme: Suitability of Health Data Australia for Australian health cohort research
- Questions:
 - How beneficial are platforms containing multiple cohorts for researchers wanting to access data? Why?
 - Would a national platform (like HeSANDA) be beneficial for YOUR cohort study?
 - Are these aspects of the HeSANDA platform valuable for your cohort study
 - Other platforms provide alternative features (eg....). Which of these features would you find useful? What other features are useful?
 - What should ARDC's next steps be?

Analysis of feedback

To ensure consistency, breakout room facilitators were provided guidance prior to each workshop on the purpose, theme and content, and encouraged to convey the question in the same format. Within the breakout room, participants were able to respond to the question verbally (documented by the facilitator) or enter their feedback directly into the document. At the end of each breakout room session, the facilitator, as guided by the participants, summarised or highlighted the key responses for each question. Breakout room responses were collated per workshop without alteration to the wording. On review, it was noted that similar responses to the questions were provided across breakout rooms. Where this occurred, the responses were viewed by the HeSANDA Program Coordinator as being of higher value and included in this report. Responses identified and collated by the breakout room facilitator are also included. Not all participant responses are included in this report

as time restraints precluded clarification of individual responses by the breakout room facilitator. The responses included in the themes below are a direct extract from the breakout room workshops and have not been modified for this report. A summary of the responses are included at the end of each question.

Benefits of sharing data

Participants were asked “**Would research/researchers benefit from being able to reuse YOUR health research data for secondary research purposes?**” Participants identified the following issues in their responses:

- Large cohorts can be used to help identify subgroups for registries or interventional studies
- Substudies can provide their data back to the main cohort study (i.e. increase size and value of the asset)
- Beneficial to make people outside of the primary community aware
- Where researchers can't collect the data themselves
 - Pool of participants is low
 - Financially - Students, early - mid career researchers where funding is not available
 - Education
- Some cohorts are more expensive to collect the data than others therefore require more effort to combine data internationally
- Large pool of data is required to answer key questions
- Enabling the completeness of information where there are gaps in data. This can't always be obtained when recruiting
- Maximise individual project potential
- Funders emphasise data sharing

Summary of participants' feedback

Overall, participants agreed that sharing data benefits researchers. Researchers use this data for secondary research projects and analyses, meta-analysis and systematic review, replication, reproducibility, &/or peer review, new study design, clinical guideline development, and policy development as a few examples.

Participants were asked “**What benefits could you get from sharing data using a platform like Health Data Australia?**” Participants identified the following benefits.

- Findable
 - Making data and research more visible is very attractive, especially in a central location; also, the capability to ‘browse’ (i.e. you might not know what’s out there or what to search for; so being able to browse around helps you discover things you might not know existed)
 - Enhance the discoverability of my datasets
 - Challenging for smaller institutes and research groups with less resources
 - Efficiencies in having one platform
 - Broader ripple effect
 - Reduces time as able to see what outputs are available for reuse. Literature review does not provide this
 - Financial impact as more requests. Maybe consider providing synthetic data where the outcome does not produce anything new
 - HDA provides more recognition/visibility

- insufficient credit/recognition given to researchers who go to the effort of making the data reusable
- Access
 - This kind of platform could change the landscape
 - Students could get access to data they could never afford to collect
 - Researchers where the data is difficult to collect
 - The request process might be helpful to our governance
 - Not duplicating effort as request are not currently visible eg US genomics db data request are visible
- Standard processes
 - Structured and standardised process for sharing that is responsive to the needs of the research community, but reflects data donor's perspectives
 - Best practice metadata management
 - Common community standards and approaches for data sharing are also attractive
- Increase research
 - A researcher/ research team has limited capacity (and ideas) and cannot possibly undertake all possible research questions
 - Useful when people apply for data - people from the institute can be part of the paper and get citations, this is especially useful for Early / Mid-Career Researchers
- Harmonisation
 - Not many platforms provide data alongside others in a coherent way. They collaborate with data standards/workflow development groups/bodies. Leveraging what's there, rather than always building new things
- Desirable functions that are not currently part of HeSANDA
 - Some more mature cohorts have reasonably mature capability for discovery/access (GenV); A priority for them would be infrastructure to help researchers after the data is shared: e.g. secure platforms, increased analytics capability, sharing analytical code
 - Finer grained metadata discovery (i.e. at the data variable-level) to allow for fine-grained search and querying
 - Study theft community style policing
 - Opportunity to provide synthetic data and the ability for researchers requesting the data to do the extraction.

Summary of participants' feedback

The [Health Data Australia](#) (HDA) platform assists by making data and research more visible (findable) and accessible to all researchers, an opportunity to standardise processes, increase the impact of the existing research, and a standard approach for requesting data. Participants also provided suggestions for desirable functions that would assist them that are currently not part of HDA i.e. secure platforms, increased analytics capability, sharing analytical code, provision of synthetic data.

Motivators

Participants were asked “**What motivates/would motivate you to share your data for secondary research purposes?**” Participants identified the following motivators.

- New collaborations
 - There is more data than people to work on cohort studies
 - Sharing data means more people to do the research
 - Collaborate with expertise that might not exist within the primary research group (e.g. AI)
 - Increased Grant applications
 - Publications / citations are motivators
- Compliance
 - Meet funder expectations
 - Provides mechanism to meet funding requirements
 - Additional use of data helps to prove the value of the existing data, which can lead to more funding
- Reduce waste
 - Spending lots of time and effort to connect their data
 - Not reinventing the wheel (pragmatic trials)
 - Unnecessary replication or duplication
 - Streamlining approvals to reduce effort and time
 - More timely access to data
 - Make the most out of the data available therefore not wasting tax payers money
 - Participants also expect data is shared and not wasted (tax payers money)
 - Ability to measure (metrics)
 - Stronger sample size
 - Pooling of data across low patient populations
 - Combine data across different populations
- Research Impact
 - Optimise impact of original research program
 - Comparative data available nationally and internationally
 - Increase funding and research in progress
 - Translation of research is faster
 - Duplication of analysis in multiple datasets (OMOP style)
 - Citations from Research datasets
- Research Integrity
 - Peer review/validation
 - Maintains ethical research
 - Upholds standards
 - fraud and data manipulation easier to identify

Summary of participants’ feedback

Participants confirmed the incentives and motivators to share data include: opportunities to develop new research questions, increased citations, new collaborations and partnerships, and keeping up with best practice. Other motivators include meeting funder requirements, promotion of using existing data to reduce waste (resource, costs), addressing ways to impact research and translation whilst ensuring research integrity.

Key research outputs

Participants were asked to “**Identify the key types of research outputs and indicate which are essential for secondary users to have access to.**” Participants were provided a few examples of research outputs and asked to indicate which were essential outputs for users to have access to. Participants could then provide additional outputs not included in the original list. Other outputs provided by participants are included below.

Key essential outputs for secondary users

	Yes	No
Data dictionary	Green	
Summary (aggregated) results	Green	
Data collection forms	Green	Red
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>identifiable</i>	Green	Red
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>de-identified</i>	Green	Red
Data analysis plans	Green	Red
Study protocol	Green	Red

NB. The responses above suggest that not all respondents believed individual participant-level data (IPD) to be an essential output for secondary users. There was no opportunity within the workshop format to investigate this further, however it is possible these respondents had not attended previous sessions and were not aware of the focus on sharing IPD for secondary research.

Other outputs

- Minimum-level reporting / datasets
- Publication plan/guidelines including authorship guidelines
- Data Management Plans
- List of publications already generated from this data set
- Metadata tags
- Data strength and limitations, representativeness of cohort - generalisability
- Consent status of those contributing data
- Licensing/conditions of use - access
- HREC protocols + PIS, Consent forms (broad/narrow), participation information form - broad or specific on reuse?
- Data user manual & data issues registers
- Data quality statements
- Laboratory manuals
- Study OPs
- CONSORT diagram
- AI models
- Synthetic datasets
- Related published reports or journal articles
- Tissues samples, biobank specimens, imaging data
- Internal reference dataset (Compare patient against) - Images, biopsy, radio tracers, dyes used, quality control datasets - to interpret participant data eg images
- Policy change eg reporting of cancer incidents - how categorise

Summary of participants' feedback

In addition to individual participant-level data, the research data dictionary and a summary (aggregated) of the results were determined as the most essential outputs, enabling researchers to use data for secondary purposes. Other less essential research outputs include data collection forms, analysis plans and protocols.

Barriers/restrictions

Participants were asked to “**Identify barriers for data providers who wish to share these research outputs.**” Using the list of research outputs, participants were asked to provide a response to each type of research output “as a data provider what are the restrictions to sharing these outputs?” Participants identified the following barriers.

- Privacy Act - Section 95A privacy act legislation and NHMRC guidelines on Australian Code for responsible conduct of research
- Consent - participant, data custodian, secondary sources of data (linkage)
- Ethics approval
- Data sharing agreements
- Lack of secure environment to share data/outputs
- Identifiability of patients on mass querying becomes an issue
- Intellectual property/copyright
- Financial cost
- Organisation policy
- External restrictions -sharing overseas, sensitive populations, commercial partnerships
- Public perceptions
- Current culture for sharing data/information

Consolidated responses from breakout rooms

Key types of research outputs	As a data provider: What are the RESTRICTIONS to sharing these outputs?
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>identifiable</i>	<p>Appropriate consent to share and distribute data</p> <p>Section 95A privacy act legislation and NHMRC guidelines on Australian Code for responsible conduct of research, Health Records and Information Privacy Act 2002 and Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022, state legislation</p> <p>Legal agreements</p> <p>Additional restrictions imposed for sharing data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overseas - Sensitive populations - AIHW rules - Commercial partnerships <p>Financial cost of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data sharing under secured and trusted environment - Resource to provide data and address any subsequent data queries. <p>Ethics approval</p> <p>Wider culture of safety of data sharing from a public perception perspective - people may not trust data being able to be shared securely.</p> <p>Lack of secure environment</p>
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>de-identified</i>	<p>Risk of re-identification - small groups</p> <p>Having appropriate consent</p> <p>Additional restrictions imposed for sharing data</p>

Assumes de-identified is not anonymised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overseas - Sensitive populations - AIHW rules - Commercial partnerships <p>Obtaining multi-site data (esp if there are EU sites where GDPR applies)</p> <p>Legal agreements</p> <p>Compliance with privacy/health legislation (assuming there's still some risk of re-identification with most datasets)</p> <p>Data sovereignty</p>
Summary (aggregated) results	<p>Data Controller/Owner sign off</p> <p>Intellectual property</p> <p>Copyright items</p> <p>Identifiability of patients on mass querying becomes an issue.</p>
Study protocol	<p>Intellectual Property</p> <p>Data Controller/Owner sign off</p> <p>Organisation policy of sharing internal documentation with external partners - Confidential vs Internal vs Public vs others</p>
Data dictionary	<p>No specific restrictions on sharing data dictionary</p> <p>Lack of standardised templates and inconsistent terms (Snomed or OMO)</p>
Data analysis plans	A lack of facilities to provide the information (a code library).
Data collection forms	Not much restriction on sharing what was collected as part of research
Additional	
Data Management Plans	Organisation policy of sharing internal documentations with external partners - Confidential vs Internal vs Public Internal documentation and processes

Summary of participants' feedback

Restrictions to share outputs varied depending on the type of output and the sensitive nature of the information/data they contained. The biggest challenges faced by providers when wanting to share data are legislation (Privacy Act - Section 95A, NHMRC guidelines on Australian Code for responsible conduct of research, Human research ethics requirements), lack of secure data sharing environments, and the current culture for sharing data/information.

Enablers

Participants were asked to **“Identify enablers for data providers who wish to share these research outputs.”** Using the list of research outputs, participants were asked to provide a response to each type of research output “as a data provider, what are the enablers for sharing these outputs?” Participants identified the following enablers.

- Having a Secure access environment for IPD.
 - controlled access platforms where data is already aggregated (like UK Biobank, where data is already prepared).
- Platforms that allow for meaningful querying ie Beacon Protocol <https://beacon-project.io/>
- Regulatory approval for data sharing
 - consent waiver
 - established processes to know who has consented

- Data management plan
 - Data dictionary - classification
 - Metadata tags or use of synthetic data
- Data sharing agreements at the organisational level rather than per project
- Established and documented processes
- Culture - provision of social licence for data sharing & transparency
- Central repositories for storage of essential documents to reduce burden on providers who aren't sharing them again and again.
- Financial - data sharing costs money! Sharing costs need to be planned for.

Consolidated responses from breakout rooms

Key types of research outputs	As a data provider: What are the ENABLERS for sharing these outputs?
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>identifiable</i>	<p>Data sharing agreements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at the organisational level, rather than at the individual project level (streamlined data access arrangements) <p>Regulatory approval</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project approval - Upfront consent - or waiver of consent from ethics. Need to understand the framework to obtain a waiver. <p>Data management plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data destruction - classification of data <p>Identifiable data might be needed for data linkage with external datasets (if permission is given)</p> <p>IT infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data storage and security level for access to it - Secure collaboration tools - Trusted data and analytics research environment (secure data enclaves, ie SERP capacity, platform with sufficient infrastructure capacity, existing secure research environments eg imaging cohort 2.5X)
Individual participant-level data (IPD) <i>de-identified</i>	<p>Data sharing agreements</p> <p>Regulatory approval</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obtaining appropriate consent - Access approval - Making clear to participants what kind of data will and won't be shared (i.e. making sure their expectations match researchers intentions) <p>Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social licence for data sharing & transparency (eg ppts may be willing to share with universities but not with pharma companies or health insurance companies) - Educating asymptomatic sub-groups is esp helpful (symptomatic groups are often more motivated to share their data) <p>Oversight of use purposes and access approval</p> <p>Data management plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - deletion plan - data de-identification guidance esp unstructured data - sensitive data management - secure method for access - classification of data <p>Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data custodian request (form/template) <p>Secure infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting data sharing framework that enable the use of TRE <p>Data sharing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of database setup and function to make this efficient and to only provide the minimum data for the

	analysis while limiting chances of the data enabling identification of participants.
Summary (aggregated) results	<p>Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metadata - Synthetic data would be something in between IPD and summary which might be sufficient <p>Standard operating procedures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - robust process of ensuring all results are captured internally and externally. <p>Web Platforms containing aggregated data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to use to visualise high level frequency - Open access/controlled access platforms where data is already aggregated (like UK Biobank, where data is already prepared). <p>Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Templates provided for key info to include in summary - Data dictionary - Beacon Protocol, helps the data be queried in a meaningful way.
Study protocol	<p>Vital for this to be shared to ensure that the people using the data understand all aspects of the study, including data collection, data set up, etc</p> <p>Share synopsis at a minimum if not sharing full protocol</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concerns re Intellectual property <p>Streamlined/Standardised protocol description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eligibility criteria - Dates & time windows of data collection (waves of data collection etc) - Consent information - sampling frame ie sample weights which are used in some social science statistical methods, - study design
Data dictionary	<p>Essential this is enabled</p> <p>Standardised concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preferably using controlled vocabularies - Standardised metadata Snomed or OMOP - so that data sets may be linked - Laboratory manuals
Data analysis plans	<p>Needs to be uniform</p> <p>This is commonly asked for, along with study design, but not commonly supplied.</p>
Data collection forms	<p>Few restrictions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intellectual Property
Additional	
Metadata tags	<p>FAIR principles embedded in management of cohort studies</p> <p>A standardised approach to understanding the characteristics of the data asset. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Retention (with specified numeric periods denoting years as 'allowed values'), - Sensitivity, - Contains Personal Information, - Whom to contact within an Organisation, - Licensing etc.
Consent status of those contributing data	<p>Common language/taxonomy for terms and conditions of consent</p> <p>Identification of participants who have provided to consent to enable sharing</p>
Licensing/conditions of use - access	Co-design an agreed framework for access and sharing
HREC approvals	Agreed HREC interpretation of need for consent for secondary use of data/ waivers of consent to do so. So that delays and misunderstandings are avoided. Also consent that may allow data to be moved into other jurisdictions
Data Management Plans	<p>Organisation policy of sharing internal documentations with external partners - Confidential vs Internal vs Public</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data quality statements - Data user manual & data issues registers
Study SOPs	<p>Standardised processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Needs to be clear who has collected data - very different interpretation if specialist vs RMO, patient, etc...

Summary of participants' feedback

Addressing the challenges and issues already identified will facilitate data sharing. For example having secure access environments, provision of social licence for data sharing & transparency, legal agreements at an organisational level rather than individual, and platforms that allow for meaningful querying and reduce the burden on providers who aren't sharing them again and again.

Data sharing practices, standards, processes, policies and systems

Participants were asked to “**Identify which cohort studies have existing standards, processes, policies and systems.**” A list of items grouped under data management, systems/technology, data policies, standard operating procedures, agreements/legal/regulatory, and resource management were provided to participants. Participants were asked to add their cohort name Yes/No to each item indicating the existence of standards, processes, policies and systems. Participants were encouraged to comment on each item where these were not in existence. Participant responses are included below.

Data management

Metadata is available at study, data asset and variable level for the majority of organisations. Good example of metadata <https://biobank.ndph.ox.ac.uk/showcase/browse.cgi?id=-2&cd=search>. Licensing may be asset specific with data dictionary study specific.

Systems/technology

Most have a data repository, catalogues and data access request systems but it appears this varies depending on size of cohort study or conglomerate of studies (MCRI). Examples of existing platforms: LifeCourse, UK Biobank, Beacon. Recognised Having a secure access platform recognised by many participants as the infrastructure gap that the HeSANDA model could provide.

Data Policies, SOP's and agreements/legal/regulatory

Most cohort studies have these as existing documents. All require HREC approval. No gaps or opportunities for ARDC identified.

Resource management

Staff capacity, capability and expertise identified by cohorts as existing although there will be a financial impact. Suggestion “we could piggy back off the HeSANDA community connect approach - whatever is developed for that”.

Other

- Suggest looking at the collaborative infrastructure that exists across Australia already -the main question for HeSANDA is where the value add could be.
- The Aus Data Archive (ADA) already provides a catalogue with study level metadata. Most large cohorts have existing platforms which provide data access so no benefit to them.
- Beacon protocol was established to overcome these challenges. Ideally, schema/guidelines can be extrapolated to other fields other than Genomics.
- Data onboarding is a challenge as the cost to secure national administrative datasets is very high.

- Creating a way to share the data without leaving the infrastructure ie SeRP
- Consent to share third party data obtained through data linkage is an issue
- Missing linkage to exposure data to determine at risk populations (environmental hazards, and socio-economic neighbourhood level data)

Summary of participants' feedback

The existence of data sharing practices, standards, processes, policies and systems varies depending on the size of the cohort study or if the study coexists with a conglomerate of studies. Large, well established cohort studies may not see the benefit of HDA as they have data repositories, access request processes, existing policies and agreements and in some cases platforms to facilitate data sharing. Smaller cohort studies are likely to be those who will gain the most from inclusion in the HeSANDA model. Having a national catalogue listing all cohort studies benefits researchers who may not be aware of some of the smaller studies in addition to raising the awareness and visibility of all cohort data irrelevant of size.

Suitability of Health Data Australia for Australian health cohort research

Participants were provided with information regarding the role of ARDC and a demonstration of the Health Data Australia (HDA) platform. Participants were asked to reflect on platforms they were aware of including HDA and to provide feedback on their view of what ARDC's next steps should be in this area. The following questions were coordinated using a live online poll. Participants' comments and the results of each question can be viewed in the section below.

"How beneficial are platforms containing multiple cohorts for researchers wanting to access data? Why?"

	High (N, %)	Moderate (N, %)	Low (N, %)	None (N, %)
Other platform benefit (n=17)	13, 76.4	4, 23.5	0, 0.0	0, 0.0

Comments

- Platforms which hold the data rather than links
- Cohorts work together such as Lifecourse
- See <https://closer.ac.uk/> as an example

"Would a national platform (like HeSANDA) be beneficial for YOUR cohort study?"

	Yes (N, %)	No (N, %)	It depends (N, %)
HeSANDA Benefit (n=14)	7, 50.0	0, 0.0	7, 50.0

Comments

- Understand the value add if there are already existing systems
- Sharing of data from other custodians is becoming more complex (ie data linkage)

"Are these aspects of the HeSANDA platform valuable for your cohort study?"

	Strongly agree (N, %)	Agree (N, %)	Neutral (N, %)	Disagree (N, %)	Strongly disagree (N, %)
National data catalogue (n=15)	9, 60.0	3, 20.0	2, 13.3	1, 6.6	0, 0.0
Data request platform (n=15)	8, 53.3	2, 13.3	3, 20.2	1, 6.6	1, 6.6
A collaborative approach to data sharing (n=15)	7, 46.6	4, 26.6	4, 26.6	0, 0.0	0, 0.0

Comments

- A collaborative approach - multiple cohorts sharing ideas on policies, procedures, systems, and learning from each other to streamline this process.

“Other platforms provide alternative features (eg....). Which of these features would you find useful? What other features are useful?”

The individual responses provided by participants to the above question are listed below and have not been altered for the report. Similar responses have been grouped and provided a theme name.

Metadata standards

- Standard practice and standard terminologies in metadata

Discovery

- Search and assimilate data across multiple studies
- Finding information about exposure data that has been used by other studies (environmental, socio-economic) and population at-risk-baseline info for neighbourhoods
- Documentation of projects being undertaken in data to avoid replication
- Accessible by international collaborators/potential collaborators

Data request management

- Good communication between platform host and users
- A single application to multiple cohort studies

Policies/practices

- Consistent licensing/data access rules
- Standard practices for sharing
- Active studies having requested the data

Reporting

- Reporting functionality eg who is requesting access to our cohort data

Analysis

- Data analysis performed

Research outputs

- Cross-section of the standard CRFs vs the data collected by the study
- Useable interactive data dictionary

Secure data access (Secure research environment)

- Secure research platform for analysis
- Secure data access capability
- Manage the link to direct data access once agreement granted

Government data

- Data exploration, analytics, environment (images, genomics, linked data), accessing multiple linked national data assets

“What should ARDC’s next steps be?”

Participants provided the following responses when asked “What ARDC’s next steps should be”. The responses have not been altered but grouped by similar themes.

Mapping exercise for shared services or collaboration

- A list of all cohort studies in Australia, cohort if consent for linkage, size of cohort, duration of data collection, state vs national, where data has to be accessed, interest in collaboration
- Consultation with existing services/platforms to coordinate services

Metadata standards

- Engage with data providers to generate a common standard for data/metadata
- Specification for data sharing and metadata exchange (eg. necessitate FHIR, beacon spec by GA4GH)

Data repository/catalogue

- Creation of data repository for use in research in order to create further research evidence
- Creation of national Australian cohort data repository
- Group the data by domain category

Secure data access (Secure research environment)

- Definition of SRE
- Accredited list of SREs in Australia

Govt data program

- Engagement with major data custodians (AIHW, state cancer/death registries)

Consent

- Engage with data providers on dynamic consent

Other

- Set up a monitoring and evaluation strategy for process improvement, then design and fund some experimental work, see what works
- [Australia's longitudinal data system](#) by Dept of Social Services that can provide some guidance on data that may be of help. It's from 2016 but has lots of detail that is still relevant

Summary of participants' feedback

With a particular focus on the applicability of the Health Data Australia platform the participants provided the following responses:

- a central place to discover and seek access to data from multiple cohorts is beneficial
- a national catalogue and request platform could be beneficial, but would have to complement and provide benefit beyond what cohort studies already have in place

Participants indicated in their responses that ARDC could assist the cohort study community by:

- developing common practices and culture around data sharing
- developing standards for metadata
- building a cohort study community of practice
- reviewing existing data policies and practices, building on the existing expertise with the goal of creating consistency
- defining secure research environments
- providing a list of accredited secure research environments
- enabling data integration and access to national linked datasets

Discussion

Summary of consultation outcomes

The consultation series established in-principle support from the participants for a national data infrastructure initiative. From an infrastructure perspective, similarities between cohort studies and clinical trials were found with respect to: data types and sensitivity; data governance and legislative requirements; information needs and requirements for data sharing and secondary use. The research benefits and motivators for data sharing were also similar. However, the current data standards and sharing practices of cohort studies proved a point of distinction from clinical trials, with a notable proportion having relatively well established and mature data management practices. As such, there was alignment between the broad priorities of cohort studies and the HeSANDA program - however an infrastructure program to support them would need to be tailored to their specific needs and practices. Key themes regarding the sharing of health cohort study data were as follows:

Research benefits of data sharing

Sharing health cohort study data benefits research by enabling secondary research projects and analyses; meta-analysis and systematic review; replication, reproducibility, &/or peer review; new study design, clinical guideline development, and policy development. Infrastructure which enables data discovery and sharing should be designed to optimally support these activities.

Information needs

In addition to individual participant-level data, the research data dictionary and a summary (aggregated form) of the results were determined to be the most essential outputs to share to enable researchers to use data for secondary purposes. Other less essential research outputs include data collection forms, analysis plans, and study protocols.

Motivators

Participants' motivators to share their data include: opportunities to develop new research questions, increased citations, new collaborations and partnerships, and keeping up with best practice. Other motivators include meeting funder requirements, promotion of using existing data to reduce waste (resource, costs), and addressing ways to impact research and translation whilst ensuring research integrity.

Current standards and practices

Current data sharing practices, standards, processes, policies and systems vary across cohort studies and are often dependent on the size of the cohort study or if the study coexists with a conglomerate of studies (i.e studies led by the same institution or investigators that apply similar data governance and management across all studies). Large, well established cohort studies tend to have more mature data management practices and established solutions for data repositories, access request processes, data policies and access agreements and, in some cases, platforms to facilitate data sharing. Smaller or newer cohort studies are less likely to have implemented these practices, and may be more challenged to identify the appropriate solutions to support their research.

Issues and challenges

Participants' ability to share their research outputs varies depending on the type of output and the sensitivity of the information it contains. Compliance with regulatory and governance requirements (e.g.

privacy legislation, Australian Code for responsible conduct of research, human research ethics requirements, on-provision of third party data) is the largest challenge faced by providers when wanting to share data, followed by the lack of secure data sharing technology. The variability in data sharing practices across cohort studies, and the average maturity level of data sharing culture within the health research community were also seen as a key issue to be addressed.

Opportunities for infrastructure development

Based on the consultation outcomes, ARDC identified a number of national infrastructure development opportunities for cohort studies.

Opportunities for the HeSANDA program

The following items align with the priorities and activities of the current HeSANDA program:

1. Development of a national platform to support discovery of Australian health cohort studies and their data assets
2. Development of a national community of practice to support Australian health cohort study data practices and culture
3. Development of community-agreed national metadata standards for health cohort studies
4. Uplift to the consistency of data policies and practices across cohort studies

Opportunities aligned to the People Research Data Commons

During the workshops, participants expressed interest in a broad range of infrastructure support. A number of these items fall outside the current scope of the HeSANDA program, but are within the scope of ARDC's [People Research Data Commons](#) ('People RDC'). The People RDC is ARDC's health portfolio aimed at delivering national scale data infrastructure for health research and translation. The portfolio consists of a series of coordinated infrastructure programs to address four key data challenges in: data strategy and data discovery, secure data access, data integration, and advanced analysis. The HeSANDA program is one such program with a specific focus on creating FAIR³ data assets from academic-led health studies. Programs within the People RDC (including HeSANDA) will address distinct priorities and outcomes but will be coordinated where stakeholders and activities overlap and organisations will be able to participate in multiple programs.

The following are items identified during consultation that align with focus areas of the People RDC (in italics) but are outside the scope of the current HeSANDA program:

- Development/support for utilising secure research environments (*Secure data access*)
- Increasing the analytics capabilities of cohort research (*Advanced analysis*)
- Developing FAIR practices for analytical code from cohort studies (*Data strategy and data discovery*)
- Improved access and use of government data for cohort study research (*Data strategy and data discovery*)

³ <https://ardc.edu.au/resource/fair-data/>

Feasibility of expanding the HeSANDA program to support Australian health cohort studies

Subject to the specific considerations and refinement, the consultations suggested that HeSANDA's scope, methods, and outputs aligns with the needs of health cohort studies in the following areas:

- A platform which improves the findability of cohort studies and their data assets across Australia
- The development of community-agreed national metadata standards
- Increasing the consistency of data policies and practices across cohort studies
- Developing communities of practice to support data practices and uplift data sharing culture at the national level

These items could provide broad benefits for cohort research and data management practices at a national level, and may be highly beneficial for new or smaller studies looking to implement appropriate research data management practices (e.g. cost efficiencies during the study design and setup stages).

However, as noted above, a larger proportion of cohort studies are well established and have mature data management practices when compared to clinical trials. Consequently, the value proposition for those studies is weighted towards the development of more granular and interoperable metadata standards which enable powerful data discovery practices such as cohort exploration. This would enable researchers to better assess the appropriateness of the data (in terms of populations studied and variables observed) before moving to a formal request. This kind of data and metadata standardisation would also have foundational benefits in terms of data integration and advanced analytics which would be in scope for future People RDC programs.

Next steps

The consultations established in-principle support for HeSANDA from the health cohort study community and identified opportunities for national infrastructure development that align with the program's scope. The strategy and activity areas of this work requires refinement via further consultation and co-design with key stakeholder groups and the HeSANDA advisory committee. During the workshops, participants expressed interest in a broad range of infrastructure support. A number of these items fall outside the current scope of the HeSANDA program, but are within the scope of the People RDC and could be considered accordingly. ARDC will consider these outcomes and the establishment of infrastructure development programs to address the needs of Australian health cohort studies which could be incorporated into its current (2023-2028) strategy.

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